

Linking Data Strategies for the José Maceda Music Collection (JMC) at the UP Center for Ethnomusicology, Manila

Katharina Flicker (TU Wien, EOSC Support Office Austria, SBA Research)

Discover how an ASEA-UNINET project aims to bridge the gaps in Southeast Asian musicological research. Despite the rich diversity of musical heritage across the region, resources are scattered and stored in varied formats, making comprehensive research challenging. Thus, a standardized data management strategy is being developed to facilitate seamless (meta) data sharing among partner organizations, revolutionizing the accessibility and efficiency of music research, all while keeping in mind the need to facilitate trust, not only in the data, but the infrastructures and organizations as well.

Collaborative Workshops in Vienna & Manila

The cooperation on linking data strategies consisted of two parts. First, a delegation from JMC visited Vienna at a workshop held April 11-15, 2024, which spanned multiple locations at the University of Music and Performing Arts Vienna (mdw) and Vienna University of Technology (TU Wien). The mdw led a session on user interfaces, engaging participants in pairs to map their ideas using Excalidraw. TU Wien's Data Science Research Unit hosted the technical segment, featuring presentations on the TU Wien Research Data repository and DAMAP¹, a machine-actionable Data Management Plan tool, the TUWRD² repository, and research on trust in data and quality indicators with an emphasis on documentation³. Additionally, the DBRepo⁴ database repository as well as the Katunog⁵ project were introduced as the University of the Philippines Center E of Ethnomusicology (UPCE) team plans to standardize metadata and explore (that is finding out whether the database and the interface can be used) the Katunog website's potential. mdw and TU Wien therefore decided to collaborate with the University of the Philippines.

Second, a Viennese delegation visited the UPCE in Manila from July 15-26, 2024: An InvenioRDM instance was set up on the UPCE computer inside of a virtual machine (VM) to later transfer the VM into the UP Data Commons infrastructure, which will allow comparative evaluation of Dataverse and Invenio systems. Additionally, a DBRepo instance was set up.

Consequently, a first, use-case upload to the UPCE Digital Audio Catalogue into DBRepo was demonstrated, which led to all participants discussing how to optimize data management within UPCE through consequent use of a central data repository infrastructure. Next, the relational schema of the UPCE Digital Audio Catalog was re-

¹ <https://damap.org>

² <https://researchdata.tuwien.ac.at>

³ K. Flicker et al., "Factors Influencing Perceptions of Trust in Data Infrastructures", International Journal of Digital Curation, vol. 18, no.1, May 15, 2024, <https://doi.org/10.2218/ijdc.v18i1.921>

⁴ <https://www.ifs.tuwien.ac.at/infrastructures/dbrepo/>

⁵ Katunog is the Open-Source Database of Philippine Indigenous Instruments Sounds: <https://katunog.qstfi.dost.gov.ph/>

structured. The original data contained in spreadsheets were re-modeled as a relational database, creating views that can be shared among researchers at the UPCE.

A key challenge was and still is the harmonization of the descriptive metadata that is currently captured in free-form semi-structured text. This will require further effort to be properly formalized and represented. However, significant parts of the data could already be “cleaned up” and imported into DBRepo. Interfaces were defined that show the same information as the original Excel spreadsheets, while supporting powerful search mechanisms. With versioning enabled, error corrections in the metadata are traceable and do not impact research results based on data exported and utilized prior to the correction having been applied.

In addition to the metadata curation, audio content was uploaded, initially into the TU Wien instance of Invenio to evaluate access control mechanisms. These turned out to be suitable for the given setting, supporting both the flexible definition of sharing rules, expiry of access rights after pre-defined time periods, as well as highlighting the need for strategic decisions concerning licensing regulations and more extensive description of the actual data collection, which motivated the set-up of an Invenio instance locally for further exploration.

The pilot provided a first glimpse of the potential of the emerging infrastructure by accessing the audio data directly from a Jupyter Notebook, extracting features, and storing these in the database. Specific templates can be made available that allow different user groups (including students as part of lab exercises) to access the data conveniently and manipulate it directly from the repository backend.

One research challenge put forward in the discussion aims at improving the audio quality, specifically correcting speed variations in the recordings, for example, those caused by fading batteries in the tape recorders during field recordings. By separating background noise from the audio and determining frequency shifts in that noise, speed changes might be detectable, which could subsequently be used for calibrating the audio, thus improving the quality of the data. This could form an exciting spin-off investigation in collaboration with the signal processing group at UP, sharing data access via the repository infrastructure.

The system administrators from DataCommons, the HPC and data infrastructure services of UP, also joined the workshop to contemplate the establishment of such a service on a more general level. They presented their high performance-computing infrastructure UP Data Commons server facility and services. With current considerations to establish a data repository based on DataVerse, DBRepo would form a suitable complement, forming a pair of repositories similar to the Invenio-DBRepo combination rolled out at TU Wien.

In a second strand of activities in Manila, a focus group discussion was held on topics related to potential security and privacy issues as well as strategies to remain trustworthy and facilitate trust in the quality of data. Specific stakeholder groups to be considered were also identified. These include in particular indigenous communities as producers of the (music is community knowledge), researchers as users and providers of data, as well as infrastructure providers and operators such as archives. Establishing the information to be collected, specifically operational procedures and adherence to them, mechanisms for control of data access, etc., and formalizing their collection and representation will be

essential to ensuring the repository infrastructure is trusted by the ever-increasing number of stakeholders interacting with it.

The power of professional data management services across the world

As in Austria, universities in Southeast Asia have started to deploy professional data management services. A similar cooperation is ongoing with several universities in Malaysia, with further partners joining. By jointly defining requirements, processes and interfaces, interoperability between such systems increases, evolving into a network of data infrastructures and services, as well as skills and competencies that support researchers in efficiently performing high-quality research. Intensifying these collaborations, the exchange of tools, services and know-how beyond national or European boundaries is considered extremely useful, not only for the Ethnomusicologists involved in this ASEA-UNINET project initiative, but for researchers across all disciplines. This will foster international collaboration, and make the highly valuable data collected in these repositories accessible to researchers globally.